

Leveraging Hyperledger Fabric for Criminal Evidence Integrity-Proofs

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Abstract. Nowadays, digital evidence plays a significant role in criminal investigations due to the widespread use of technology in daily life. As in the case of physical evidence, digital evidence requires suitable and secure handling and storage processes to guarantee its integrity and be admissible in a court. This paper presents a blockchain-based integrity-proof system that leverages the security features of Hyperledger Fabric to enable secure and reliable evidence. This system also enhances the usability of the blockchain technology, allowing authorities with no technical knowledge to use it. The design and specific implementation are described in detail, resulting in a real prototype for a reliable, secure, and user-friendly criminal evidence integrity-proof system. This system has been successfully demonstrated in the analysis of car accidents, resulting in a very useful tool for securing car accident 3D reconstruction and energetic analysis.

Keywords: Blockchain, Hyperledger Fabric, crime records, evidence, integrity, transparency

1 Introduction

Nowadays, many criminal law cases depend on evidence, including physical evidence (e.g., objects, clothing, etc.), scientific evidence (e.g., DNA, ballistics, etc.) and Witness testimonies (e.g., crime victims, witnesses, etc.). Evidence is the objective and impartial information that would provide credibility and reliability in a court, enabling appropriate decisions to be made about a crime. However, a new type of evidence has recently started to be often considered: digital evidence. It refers to information stored or transmitted in binary form that can be retrieved from various sources such as computer hard drives, mobile phones, smartwatches, or other electronic devices. Although this type of evidence was initially associated with electronic crimes such as pornography or credit card, fraud, digital evidence now plays a pivotal role in all kinds of crimes. For instance, emails, mobile phone records, photos, videos, etc. can provide crucial insights into a crime.

The chain of custody is a fundamental aspect of evidence management, ensuring the integrity and admissibility of physical evidence in legal proceedings. The handling and transfer of evidence need to be documented in detail from its collection up to its presentation through a chain of custody that safeguards its reliability and credibility, thereby upholding the principles of fairness and justice. It is already noted in the 'NIST Inter-agency Report NIST IR 8387: Digital Evidence Preservation; Considerations for Evidence Handlers' [4] that current digital evidence introduces novel challenges in addition to those encountered with traditional physical evidence: digital files are very easy to change, so maintaining their integrity is a critical concern.

In this sense, this work proposes an innovative criminal evidence integrity-proof system backboned by blockchain technology for securely guaranteeing the integrity of criminal evidence. Blockchain inherently provides integrity as it is resistant to tampering, making information recorded on it a trusted source of evidence for authorities [5]. Moreover, data on the blockchain is directly accessible to all authorized parties at once, enhancing transparency and reducing costs and time associated with individual communications [6]. The main contribution of this work is the detailed design, implementation, and application of a real prototype of a blockchain-based integrity system to improve not only the security but also the usability of current blockchain-based digital evidence management systems.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 starts with an overview of current blockchain-based evidence integrity solutions, identifying their main limitations that have motivated this research. Section 3 presents the design and implementation of the proposed evidence integrity system. Section 6 describes some experiments carried out for its validation with criminal evidence of a car accident. Lastly, Section 5 draws the main conclusions and future work of the research.

2 State of the art

Blockchain has emerged as an immutable ledger of distributed nodes which maintain a copy of the stored information previously validated by a consensus protocol and grouped into blocks. Each block is linked to the previous one through cryptography (integrity is guaranteed), transactions are digitally signed by their creators (originator is identifiable), and central controlling authorities are not needed anymore (decentralization and transparency are enhanced).

There are different types of blockchain technologies. The first ones that appeared were public networks where participation is unrestricted (i.e., Bitcoin, Ethereum). These networks have already been considered for evidence integrity [6], [8], [7]. However, private networks soon gained importance for sectors requiring usage restriction to authorized participants, such as that related to authorities and criminal evidence. In private networks, a governing entity (a set of participants) often oversees the entry of new participants and determines their permissions. Hyperledger Fabric stands out as the most prominent private blockchain network, offering privacy, robustness, scalability, and improved performance over public technologies. Hyperledger Fabric is extensively with expanded as proven by successful deployments from giant enterprises such as

Walmart's food supply chain [16], Fujitsu's water trading platform [17] and IBM suppliers onboarding solution [18].

Hyperledger Fabric technology has been extensively considered as a trustworthy guarantee of integrity for all kind of information, including domains such as healthcare [1], IoT [2] or supply chains [3]. More recently, its applicability to criminal investigation processes has been identified as optimal. Some research works in this context are [9], [10], [11], [12], [13] have already demonstrated the suitability of the Hyperledger Fabric technology to address inherent security weaknesses in conventional integrity solutions for digital evidence. However, there is still limited research into focusing on practical implementations aimed at bolstering security while also prioritizing usability, especially for sectors in which users do not usually have technical knowledge, and even less, about technologies as complex and innovative as blockchain. Furthermore, the technical particularities of using the Hyperledger Fabric have not been deeply explained, leading to a greater lack of knowledge about the solution and limiting its application by making its particularization more difficult. In this context, this paper proposes a secure and user-friendly Hyperledger based evidence integrity system focusing on deep technical details description as well as on a real scenario involving evidences for a car accident.

3 Evidence Integrity-Proof system description

The proposed integrity system provides a highly secure and transparent platform for digital evidence integrity validation using blockchain and smart contracts, specifically using Hyperledger Fabric technology. Information records storage in the blockchain means the generation of a transaction and its recording in the blockchain network. This process can be expensive in time due to the distributed nature of the blockchain network, making the storage process a natively asynchronous process. To deal with this asynchronous characteristic of the storage process from a client perspective, smart contracts can emit blockchain events to the outside network, so that for each archived/modified information record, an event is emitted and received in a different system. By this way, users can request the storage of information records synchronously and subscribe asynchronously to events to be notified when the information record is successfully stored in the blockchain.

Digital evidence is normally made up by different kinds of files of usually high size that are not suitable to be recorded on blockchain due to disk space restrictions that cannot be easily solved. Therefore, this integrity system avoids storing files in blockchain and keeps evidence in a local storage inside the authorities' premises, such as traditional databases or Inter Planetary File System (IPFS) among others. By this way, the disk space issues are solved providing, not only, better performance but also enhanced security, as evidence is often considered sensitive and should not be stored in a blockchain in which removal is not possible. For this reason, evidence is not directly stored in blockchain, instead, hashes of the evidence are stored on the blockchain, as they do not disclose any sensitive input data but can be useful for guaranteeing that information has not been altered. SHA2-256 has been considered suitable for this

system as it is widely standardized, it is secure enough and with a good trade-off between security and performance [19]. Later, when it is necessary to verify whether evidence has been altered, the current evidence value is retrieved from the local storage, the hash function is applied, and the result can be compared with the hash value previously stored in the blockchain. If they match, the evidence can be considered trustworthy and admissible in the court.

Taking this into consideration, Fig. 1 shows the high-level architecture of the integrity-proof system, where the main five components can be identified in different colors. The following sections describe each of them in detail.

Fig. 1. Evidence integrity-proof system high-level architecture.

3.1 Blockchain network and smart contracts

A Hyperledger Fabric network has been considered as it is the most widespread permissioned blockchain network. Currently, for prototype purposes, three organizations with two nodes and one certification authority each one, are available. However, in a real deployment, more nodes, and more organizations to guarantee decentralization and transparency, or even making use of existing well-known solutions such as Alastria [14] or European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI) [15].

Hyperledger Fabric, show in orange in Fig. 1, provides a highly secure, transparent, and decentralized infrastructure for building distributed applications. Identity management is crucial for ensuring that only authorized users can access recorded evidence and interact with the system. The Hyperledger Fabric Certificate Authority (CA) plays a pivotal role in providing a secure and reliable identity management solution within the Hyperledger Fabric. In Hyperledger Fabric, every user dealing with the system receives a digital identity comprising a unique public-private key pair. In this sense, the CA issues, revokes, and manages digital certificates that contain the user's public key, identity information, and other relevant metadata. The creation of a new identity in the blockchain requires an enrollment process in which the user submits a request to the

CA to create a new identity. The CA verifies the user's identity (i.e, verifying the user's email address, phone number, or other identifying information) and generates the public-private key pair for the user. The user's public key is then stored in the blockchain network, along with other additional identity information. Within Hyperledger Fabric, the smart contract defines the business logic of the integrity system and the rules for submitting, retrieving, and validating evidence. A simple and generic data model has been defined for the evidence integrity-proofs through hashes. The data model includes the following fields:

- file id: it refers to the identification of a specific piece of evidence.
- file description: it refers to a description of the specific evidence for usability purposes.
- file hash: it refers to the summary of the evidence considered as a suitable proof of integrity.
- timestamp: it refers to the specific time the writing operation has happened.

As explained, every time new information is stored on the system, a blockchain event is automatically generated from the smart contract with the provided data to feed the blockchain monitor and provide a user-friendly graphical way to access the recorded information. The event provides the following information:

- version: it refers to the version of the data model to easily allow potential future modifications or extensions if needed.
- owner: it refers to the specific user who has provided the evidence information.
- data: it refers to the information provided about the evidence following the defined data model.
- id: it refers to the identification of the blockchain transaction the event has been generated from.

Registered information is only accessible (through retrieval or verification functionalities) to authorized users based on an access control based on the digital certificates issued by the CA. To guarantee the confidentiality of the information, authorized users can only view or verify the information they are owners of.

3.2 REST API FABRIC

The integrity system exposes a REST API, show in blue in Fig. 1, for allowing external interaction with either the blockchain network and the implemented smart contracts. The API exposes the following services: identity, user and blockchain services.

The Identity Service is responsible for obtaining users' crypto material needed for the signature of blockchain requests. It also provides authentication against Fabric CA through sign-in, refresh and sign-out processes. Any API requiring interaction with the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain network requires a Fabric SDK Client. The generation of this Fabric SDK Client requires the crypto material to be stored in the users' wallets. To obtain this crypto material, a valid JWT access token is needed in the HTTP "Authorization" header from the request. A middleware to automatize the process on every request has been designed and implemented to perform the following steps for validating the received in the Authorization header of the request:

- It verifies if it belongs to a valid existing user.

- It verifies the token has not expired.
- It takes the enrollment ID claim from the access token.
- It extracts the crypto material associated with the enrollment ID from user wallet.
- It generates a Fabric Client SDK ready to interact with Hyperledger Fabric blockchain network.
- It adds this Fabric SDK Client to the following requests.

The User Service manages the users' lifecycle inside Hyperledger Fabric. All the requests require the access token from the authentication step. This service includes the following activities: register a new user in an organization, list the users of a given organization, get information from a given user of an organization, update a user of an organization and delete a user from an organization.

The blockchain Service provides interacts with the network nodes to obtain information about blockchain Network (i.e., channels, transactions, or smart contract details) and to submit transactions allowing invoking and querying smart contract functions to store, list or verify evidence integrity information. As in the previous case, it also requires the access token from the authentication step.

3.3 REST API DATA

The integrity system exposes a REST API DATA, show in yellow in Fig. 1, for managing the information to be recorded following the data model considered by the smart contract. This API uses the functionality exposed by REST API FABRIC to interact with the deployed smart contracts. This API does not persist any data; it acts as a proxy towards REST API FABRIC and all the provided data is only stored in the Hyperledger Fabric network. The API exposes the criminal case documents service for:

- Create: It creates a new integrity-proof following the defined data model.
- List: It gets the list of registered integrity-proofs from the user.
- Get: It retrieves the integrity-proof information of a given file id.
- Verify: it performs an integrity verification for a given file id comparing the current file hash with the previously recorded hash in the smart contract at creation of the asset.

3.4 Verification dashboard

The verification dashboard, show in purple in Fig. 1, is a web application for authorities to interact with the REST API BC to provide integrity-proofs in a user-friendly and graphical way. It is only available for registered users (authentication is needed to obtain a valid JWT access token). This dashboard allows two different operations:

- Integrity-proof registration: It refers to the registration of the hash associated to specific evidence. It internally requests REST API DATA a new criminal case creation service. As shown in Fig. 2a, the user needs to select the "Register File" Tab and provide a specific file ID that will identify it in the system, a file description to provide additional useful details to describe the file and select the specific file whose integrity require to be proved. The file is selected from the local hard disk and its hash is automatically calculated. Once the information has been correctly

the format and parse the content to the events broker, the second component. The events broker, implemented using Elastic Search, categorizes the information from the different blockchain events to show the information in different tables on the dashboard. Finally, the blockchain monitor dashboard, the third component, is implemented using Kibana. It provides a graphical interface to show the information extracted from the blockchain events. Fig. 3 shows an example of the dashboard for a specific user with two registered evidence proof of integrity.

4 Evidence Integrity-Proof system description

The use of blockchain for verifying the integrity of criminal evidence has been successfully demonstrated in the analysis of car accidents. Car accidents present a compelling scenario where maintaining the chain of custody is paramount, particularly in instances where advanced techniques such as 3D reconstruction and energy analysis are employed using photogrammetry and computer vision [21], [22]. While these procedures are largely automated, they still necessitate expert input, such as in deformation analysis. Therefore, ensuring the traceability of operations is essential to confirm that the determined impact speed has not been compromised or altered in any way.

To this end, a standalone tool that allows the 3D reconstruction and energetic analysis of car accidents using images taken with any type of camera, even mobile phones, was developed. Due to the sensitive information that can be stored in the car accident, the blockchain-based integrity-proof system was integrated within the standalone tool, so the different images (evidence) used for the accident reconstruction can be secured. In particular, to incorporate blockchain technology, the standalone tool integrated a module named “Protect Project”, which calls the REST API DATA to generate and store a unique hash code (SHA-256) for each file. Once the hash is correctly stored in the blockchain, the tool indicates that the file has been securely registered as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Car accident evidence registration in the integrity-proof system.

Finally, to verify that the files (evidence) within the tool have not been modified since they were registered in the integrity-proof system, the tool includes another module named “Check Project” that calls the REST API DATA to verify the hash codes of the files. Then, the tool indicates to the user whether the file has been modified or not, as shown in Fig. 5.

FILE	HASH	STATUS
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-52-58.png		Protected
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-00.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-02.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-04.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-06.png		Protected
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-08.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-09.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-53-11.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-54-13.png		Modified
snap_3840x2160_2022-06-10_10-54-15.png		Modified

Fig. 5. Car accident evidence hash codes verification.

5 Conclusions

This paper improves the security and usability of current criminal evidence chain of custody solutions in which evidence integrity is required. For this purpose, a blockchain-based evidence integrity system has been designed, implemented, and validated for integrity validation of car accidents evidence. This novel integrity system is based on the Hyperledger Fabric technology, leveraging blockchain inherent security features such as integrity, traceability, and availability. Furthermore, usability of Hyperledger Fabric has been enhanced through the creation of REST API for easy automatic interaction, as well as the inclusion of a blockchain monitor to enable high usability and isolate users from the use of blockchain as backbone. As a result, a real prototype for more reliable, secure, and user-friendly evidence integrity validation has been presented and described in detail with emphasis on the technical particularities of using Hyperledger Fabric. Additionally, the main improvements over the state-of-the-art methods were also identified.

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